

CULTURAL HERITAGE IN RURAL
REMOTE AREAS FOR CREATIVE
TOURISM AND SUSTAINABILITY

METHODOLOGICAL GUIDE **for the development of Living Labs** **within the Culturality project**

LA PONTE, Research Centre and Ecomuseum

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INTRODUCTION

These methodological guidelines are based on more than ten years of experience in coordinating social and cultural innovation labs in rural areas. The approach integrates elements drawn from Living Labs, Citizen Labs and entrepreneurship and innovation methodologies (e.g., the Lombard method, Lean Startup), as well as methodological advances developed in the contexts of territorial mediation, community work and open science (Fernández, 2023).

The Living Labs in the Culturality project (Fuente, 2024) are spaces for collaborative experimentation that seek to trigger local processes of cultural, social and economic innovation, strengthening the diversity of actors and cooperation between citizens, the voluntary sector, institutions and emerging entrepreneurial projects. We understand the laboratories as spaces where diverse groups—in terms of age, profession, experience, background, education or gender—come together to collaborate, explore and learn collectively around complex ideas or problems, which they address through processes of experimentation and prototyping (Fernández, 2026).

Lab Development

1

PHASE 1
Idea/Initial Project
(Promoter)

2

PHASE 2
Collaboration Building
(Minimum 5 collaborators)

3

PHASE 3
Co-creation of the Prototype
(All together)

These labs are open to anyone and are designed as environments that actively promote diversity. Participants voluntarily organise themselves into interdisciplinary teams, and each group develops its own prototyping process. The teams consist of a lead promoter and several collaborators. The lab's host organisation provides these teams with coordination, facilitation, mentoring, and general documentation.

The labs represent the next phase to be implemented within the Culturality project, following the 'Rural Spot'* activities carried out in each participating region. An analysis of the results of these activities enables us to identify the specific areas on which to focus the call for ideas for each workshop.

Prototyping work carried out as part of the Ruralab project (La Ponte)

PREPARING THE *LIVING LAB*

Establishment of the coordination team:

The recommended minimum team should consist of the following people:

- 1 coordinator (from the organisation responsible for the Living Lab).
- 1 or 2 mediators, 1 or 2 mentors and 1 person responsible for documenting and project process analysis.

* Rural Spots are meetings for stakeholders involved in tangible and intangible cultural heritage, craft industries and local entrepreneurship. Their main aim is to gain a realistic understanding of the current situation in these areas within rural communities. They help to identify existing challenges and potential synergies that could contribute to the design and development of future Living Labs.

The coordinator must be involved throughout the entire process. They must understand how the process works as a whole, as well as plan and organise their team and the activities to be carried out.

The mediators will participate throughout the process, from the first call for applications until the deadline, as well as during the in-person implementation of the lab.

Mediators must possess the following characteristics:

- Be familiar with the local territory.
- Be able to translate the call for proposals into clear, non-academic language, and visit the locations where organisations or individuals potentially interested in the call are based.
- Promote a diversity of profiles among participants when selecting promoters and collaborators to work with the coordinating team.
- Have training in conflict resolution.
- Be able to manage internal dynamics during the workshop: foster a collaborative ecosystem that extends beyond the project itself, including the prototyping phase; view mediation as a key tool to help transform the promoter's idea into something collective; explain the purpose and objectives of the process not only at the start, but also reinforce them in each session; as well as supporting and accompanying everyone involved in the process.

Mentors will work during the in-person delivery of the workshop. The search for suitable candidates may take place during the process, but they must be taken into account from the outset, as, like the facilitator, they must be paid from the overall budget. Although mentors are more heavily involved during the prototyping phase, it is advisable for them to participate in the selection of ideas to assess whether the prototypes can realistically be developed.

The person responsible for documenting and analysing the process will be in charge of documenting the entire lab process in accordance with the methodological guidelines for documentation (Section 11). The use of a common documentation methodology across all labs developed within the Culturality framework facilitates the collection and systematisation of data, thereby aiding its subsequent analysis.

Establishing a timetable for the entire process

Given that the total duration of the process must be at least three months, the first decision to be made is whether the prototyping phase—that is, the face-to-face phase with the working groups—will be carried out intensively (5–7 days) or extensively (over two months, with weekly sessions, or over one month with intensive weekend sessions). Once this has been decided, we can draw up the schedule.

Examples of schedules:

Selection of the physical space where the in-person prototyping phase will take place:

Recommended venues include cultural centres, schools, community spaces, libraries, museums, and so on. Generally speaking, these are places that encourage community interaction. The venues should be open and flexible, with a good internet connection, adequate lighting and sufficient power sockets for devices and equipment. It is also important to have movable tables and chairs that allow the space to be rearranged according to the dynamics of the work, as well as whiteboards or other surfaces on which to display posters or sheets of paper.

It is also recommended to choose locations that are accessible by public transport and have hotels, hostels or other types of accommodation nearby.

CALL FOR IDEAS

The organising entity does not propose ideas of its own. It merely indicates the thematic areas towards which ideas should be directed.

Those submitting proposals for this call may be either individuals or organisations (bearing in mind that each organisation may only be represented by one person). From the outset, they must understand that:

- Their participation is voluntary and unpaid (except in contexts where this is not culturally feasible).
- The process will be open, collaborative and documented.
- The results will be made public.

- It is important to prevent conflicts relating to authorship, intellectual property or commercial interests, so this must be clearly communicated from the outset.

How to launch the call for proposals, and how do applicants/promoters submit their ideas?

Posters or leaflets can be produced for distribution on each institution's social media channels and in public spaces. An online form is a very useful tool for enabling interested individuals or organisations to submit their applications.

For further details on the contents of call of ideas, please refer to ANNEX 1.

TERRITORIAL MEDIATION AND INCLUSION

This process runs concurrently with the call for ideas. Mentors must present the Living Labs within the local area, communicating the proposal to the entire population in a clear and accessible manner.

Objective: to reach out to stakeholders who do not usually participate, as innovation is strengthened through diversity.

Actions:

- Translate the language of the call for proposals into accessible formats and terms.
- Be present in spaces where potential participants may exclude themselves due to cultural, administrative or digital barriers.

Rural Spots enable this work to be directed more efficiently, as their implementation has facilitated the identification of organisations or individuals who might be interested in applying to the call for proposals.

When participant profiles are too homogeneous, the potential for social innovation is reduced. Diversity is a methodological objective, not merely an ethical one.

SELECTION OF IDEAS

The coordination team (coordinator, mediators and mentors) selects between two and six ideas. The exact number will depend on the budget and the space available to run the prototyping workshop. Bear in mind that, even with the same budget (€20,000) across the countries involved in the Living Lab, costs are higher in some areas than in others.

It is also important to bear in mind that the number of applications to the call for proposals may be low due to the dispersed nature of the population and the long distances involved.

However, quality takes precedence over quantity. In other words, carrying out the process in accordance with the proposed methodology is more important than the number of prototypes developed or the total number of participants.

The criteria for the selection of ideas should be clearly outlined in the call for ideas (see ANNEX 1).

CALL FOR APPLICATIONS AND SELECTION OF CONTRIBUTORS

Once the ideas have been selected, they will be made public so that interested parties can choose the one or ones that most appeal to them. It is at this point that the call for collaborators is launched (see ANNEX 2).

Collaborators will be selected with a view to ensuring:

- Diversity in terms of gender, age, educational background, experience, profession, etc.
- The inclusion of participant profiles with disruptive potential. It is important to avoid excessive similarity between participants.
- A balanced combination of technical and community perspectives.

This step requires the coordination team to define criteria. Between 5 and 7 collaborators should be selected for each idea.

In this way, working teams will be formed, comprising the person who proposed the idea (the promoter) and the collaborators.

Summary: there are two ways of voluntary participation:

As a promoter.

1

This is the person who proposes the idea from which the prototyping process will start. The promoter will be present during the laboratory, developing his/her idea together with the collaborators, and accepting the new proposals or changes that are decided collectively.

As a collaborator.

2

They will join one of the work teams developing the prototypes. They will be present throughout all the days of laboratory and, thanks to their experience, training or skills, they will enrich the process by contributing ideas and different perspectives.

IDENTIFICATION OF TECHNICAL MENTORS OR EXTERNAL EXPERTS

The role of the specialist mentor is independent of the coordination team. Once the ideas have been selected, a list of external personnel can be drawn up to address any specific technical needs that may arise. Their involvement is limited to a few hours, working with the teams to resolve specific problems.

Example:

If an idea requires the development of a mobile app and there are no members of the working group with IT skills, a professional should be brought in to contribute on an ad hoc basis to the development of the prototype (preferably with a pre-agreed hourly rate).

OPENING SESSION TO INTRODUCE THE TEAMS

Before the Living Lab begins, a meeting is held (which may take place online) with the following objectives:

- For the promoter to present their project.
- To introduce each collaborator and outline their role or area of interest.
- To clearly explain how the Living Lab works:
 - Stages.
 - Working methods.
 - Potential conflicts or tensions and how they will be managed.
 - Advantages of the format in terms of innovation.

Teams should be prevented from organising themselves informally (e.g., WhatsApp groups without mediation), as this can: lead conflicts, misunderstandings and loss of methodological rigour.

DEVELOPMENT OF THE PROTOTYPING WORKSHOP

As for the duration of the workshop, the options are:

- **Intensive (concentrated sessions** → greater creativity, but less accessible. The duration would be one week. It should be kept in mind that people in employment, as well as those with care responsibilities (for example, for children or elderly relatives), may not have the time to attend an intensive workshop.

- **Extensive (weeks/months)** → more inclusive, but with a risk of losing focus. For example, it could be spread over every weekend for a month.

Both formats can be combined (for example, intensive creative sessions alongside longer periods for technical development or processes requiring more time).

Stages of the Living Lab:

The laboratory workflow should be organised into four stages, which are set out and described below:

1. Problem definition

An idea is put under pressure to explore its potential, and through a process of collaborative and immersive research, possible developments are analysed. When faced with a specific problem, specific solutions are sought. An individual (or a group) puts forward an idea that addresses a need. This idea is shared with others who have different knowledge, backgrounds and interests. It is questioned, broken down, reconstructed and may be transformed into a different approach, albeit one derived from the original. It is the working group, within the specific space of the laboratory, that tests the multiple possible solutions to the problem posed.

2. Prototyping

Ideas are brought to life in a prototype: a quick, low-cost, scaled-down test. Through experimentation (trial and error), the characteristics of a product, service, device, organisation, methodology or practice are defined and developed within a fluid environment of shared knowledge. Prototyping aims to create a partial representation, in the form of an object or procedure, that is sufficiently developed and concrete to be tested, evaluated and improved.

And what can be prototyped? Practically anything: objects, infrastructure, devices, services, organisations, practices, processes or methodologies. The only condition is that

Work sessions during the 1st Rural Experimenta, a rural laboratory for experimentation and citizen innovation (Villanueva de Santo Adriano, May 2019)

they can be developed as scalable processes or objects within a limited time and space (the laboratory).

3. Testing

Prototypes are validated. It is necessary to check whether they can be put into practice, whether they make sense, whether they are viable, operational and scalable, and whether they meet the need for which they were designed. They must be validated with the target group, community, space, etc.

This allows us to listen to potential users, identify problems or faults and resolve them quickly, incorporating the concerns and feedback of those affected by the challenge at hand. All of this helps to avoid unnecessary effort and costs.

Prototypes are created at scale precisely to anticipate potential impacts should difficulties arise. That is why a prototype is always beneficial: if it works, we gain because it can be replicated; and if it does not work, we also gain, as we will have saved time, money and complications.

This workflow is designed so that we can go back at any time, return to the problem-definition phase and prototype again.

4. Communication

Finally, when it comes to collaborative knowledge production, this knowledge must necessarily be accessible, open and understandable to different audiences. In this way, anyone will be able to reproduce and replicate this process.

In the case of those ideas which, by the consensus of each team, are to be patented or turned into market products, it is also essential to know how to communicate and position them appropriately.

The challenge, therefore, lies in being able to communicate the results of the prototype—both positive and negative—to different audiences and potential users. This is important because it is not just a matter of showcasing success or offering a biased view of what innovation entails: innovation also involves making many mistakes until, based on those lessons, a cutting-edge design, revolutionary product, technological advancement or disruptive idea emerges.

Important Note: The laboratory must have a dedicated physical space for care, known as a 'care space'. In a situation where a considerable number of people, who do not know one another, are required to work together and spend several hours in close proximity in a relatively confined space, it is inevitable that stressful situations will arise.

It is therefore essential to pay attention to emotional well-being throughout the entire process, taking into account the diversity of personalities, paces, and ways of interacting and communicating among individuals. The 'care space' plays a key role in alleviating any

tensions that may arise. It is a quiet area, separate from other activities and dedicated exclusively to this purpose, where participants can sit for a while and have a coffee or a tea; in short, to switch off. Any participant may use this space during the workshop sessions and, if they wish, receive support from the coordination team.

The prototyping workshop should conclude with an event open to the public, providing an opportunity to share the results achieved. The event could finish with the collective celebration, for which it is recommended to set aside some funds from general budget.

CROSS-CUTTING DOCUMENTATION ACTIVITIES

Documentation is a **cross-cutting and ongoing activity** that should be carried out **throughout the project process**, not just at the end. Its aim is to record, in a simple and systematic way, how the workshop unfolds, what decisions are made, who is involved, the criteria applied, and what lessons are learnt along the way. Documentation is key to both internal evaluation and future improvement, as well as the potential replication of the model.

Alignment with the *Living Labs* methodological framework

This approach to documentation is consistent with the methodological principles set out in this document and with **action research** methodologies:

- Documentation is understood as part of the **experimentation process itself**, not as a subsequent task.
- Value is placed not only on the results but also on the interactions, decisions and tensions that emerge during the course of the lab.
- The use of tools such as the *Lab Cube* encourages **reflection within the teams themselves**, whilst the perspective of the documentarian provides an external layer of analysis.

- The combination of internal records and external observations allows for a situated interpretation, consistent with real contexts and with the logic of collective learning characteristic of Living Labs.

General principles

- Documentation begins in the phases prior to the lab, particularly during the local engagement process and the call for ideas.
- The task must be **explicitly assigned to one person**, referred to in this document as the *documentarian*.
- The project mentors and mediators must **remind participants of and reinforce this procedure** at the end of each day. The documentation comprises:
 - Records produced by the participating teams,
 - External observations made by the documentarian.

Basic documentation tools

The documentation of the process relies on a number of complementary tools. Not all of them are used in the same way or by the same people, but **the documentarian is responsible for coordinating their use and ensuring that the documentation is carried out correctly.**

Tools:

- **Notebook (paper or digital)**

A tool used directly by the documentarian. Used to record field observations, group dynamics, incidents, informal decisions and reflections throughout the entire process.

- **Record of agreements at the end of each session (simple minutes)**

A brief document that summarises, at the end of each day, the agreements reached, the decisions taken and the next steps. It can be drawn up collaboratively, but its correct completion must be supervised by the documentarian.

- **Lab Cube documentation tool** (see ANNEX 3)

A tool used by participating teams to document their own work process in phases.

The documentarian does not document on behalf of the teams, but is responsible for: explaining how the tool works, answering queries, ensuring that all teams are using it, and verifying that all phases of the process are correctly recorded.

The final project documentation is a combination of the material produced by the teams in the *Lab Cube* and the records and observations made by the documentarian.

Roles of the documentarian

The documentarian is responsible for:

- Recording the process in a straightforward and ongoing manner from the outset.
- Supporting the teams and ensuring that they, in turn, document their work properly.
- Providing an external perspective on the process, acting as an observer or participant-observer.
- Organising and systematising the information generated throughout the project.

Stages of the process to be documented

Prior local mediation

The first stage to be documented is the preliminary work on local mediation, which takes place in parallel with the call for ideas.

Issues to be documented

- Mapping of stakeholders, roles and interests.
- Locations and contexts in which mediation takes place.
- Materials used (simplified versions of the call for participation, presentations, etc.).
- Reactions, points of resistance and expectations of the communities.

Guiding questions

1. Which actors and communities have been involved?
2. How and where was the call for proposals publicised?
3. What facilitation materials were used?

4. How did people react?
5. What difficulties or barriers were identified?

Documentation relating to the call for ideas

This section outlines how the call for ideas works and how selection decisions are made.

Issues to be documented

- Number and type of ideas submitted.
- Who submits the ideas.
- Selection criteria and procedures.
- Alignment of decisions with the project methodology.

Guiding questions

1. How many ideas have been put forward, and what sort of ideas are they?
2. Who is putting them forward?
3. What criteria have been used to select them?
4. Who has made the decisions, and how?
5. Have the recommended guidelines and procedures been followed?

Call for collaborators

This stage is crucial to ensuring that teams are balanced and effective.

Issues to be documented

- Profiles registered as contributors.
- Roles required within the teams.
- Criteria used to form the groups.

Guiding questions

1. What types of people took part?

2. Did the call ensure a diverse range of participants?
3. How was a balance struck between shared interests and diversity within the teams?
4. What difficulties arose during this phase?

Laboratory documentation

The development of the laboratory is documented across its four phases:

- Problem definition
- Prototyping
- Testing
- Communication

The teams document their process using the *Lab Cube* (see ANNEX 3), whilst the documentarian verifies its use and supplements the information with external observations.

Guiding questions

1. How has each team approached each phase?
2. What problems or obstacles have arisen?
3. What conflicts have arisen and how have they been resolved?
4. Have all teams properly documented the process using their *Lab Cube* device?
5. What external observations would you make to help improve the process?

Closure and final report

Using all the information gathered, the documentarian must:

- Collect all the *Lab Cubes*.
- Unpack them and digitise them (by photographing or scanning).
- Organise the material in accordance with the stages of the process.
- Produce a final report combining description, summary and reflection.

Guiding questions

1. Is the documentation for all phases complete?
2. What materials are included in the final report?
3. What are the key lessons learned from the process?
4. What aspects could be improved in future editions?

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Lab promotional flyer. Proyecto Ruralab. La Ponte.

■ ANNEX I EXAMPLE OF A CALL FOR IDEAS

Culturalitylab: TRADITIONAL CRAFTS AND KNOWLEDGE: HERITAGE ASSETS FOR SUSTAINABLE TOURISM IN RURAL AREAS

Introduction

The La Ponte Research Centre and Ecomuseum invites interested parties to submit ideas aimed at developing prototypes within an experimental laboratory focused on traditional crafts and knowledge as heritage assets for sustainable tourism in rural areas.

This experimental laboratory has the following objectives:

- To preserve and safeguard traditional knowledge and expressions of intangible cultural heritage linked to local crafts.
- To build collaborative networks between craftspeople, institutions, the tourism sector and other local stakeholders.
- To promote community-led management of sustainable rural tourism projects, strengthening local governance and participatory decision-making.

What will the workshop involve?

An individual or group submits an idea through this call for proposals with the aim of developing it collaboratively and creating a prototype.

A committee made up of the ecomuseum team will select up to five projects. A second call will then be published, aimed at those interested in collaborating on the development of the selected ideas.

The promoters of the chosen projects, together with those selected as collaborators, will meet in person in Villanueva de Santo Adriano (Asturias) to take part in a five-day workshop to be held in September 2026. The aim will be to develop prototypes or initial versions of the selected ideas.

The working groups will be supported by a team responsible for facilitation, coordination and mentoring throughout the process. The prototypes developed will be presented publicly by the project leaders and collaborators on the final day of the workshop.

What kinds of ideas can be submitted?

Proposals should focus on at least one of the following areas:

- **Revitalisation and transmission of traditional craft skills.** Projects focused on documenting, teaching across generations and promoting techniques, knowledge and cultural expressions linked to local crafts, as well as the recovery of tangible and intangible cultural heritage as a cornerstone of rural sustainability.
- **Innovation and design with cultural identity.** Initiatives that integrate traditional knowledge with new approaches to design, product improvement and adaptation to responsible markets, without losing cultural identity.
- **Building regional networks and partnerships.** Projects that foster collaboration between craftspeople, public institutions, the tourism sector, academia and other local stakeholders, with the aim of strengthening value chains and cooperation.
- **Community-based rural tourism and participatory governance.** Proposals that promote community self-management, sustainable tourism and the strengthening of organisational capacities for collective decision-making.

We welcome ideas that can be designed, built or developed as an initial version or prototype, in accordance with the conditions set out in this call for proposals, and which are carried out collaboratively.

The idea may be entirely new or form part of an ongoing process. It does not need to be fully defined, as the aim is precisely to shape and develop it together with others who will be involved in its implementation.

Who can participate?

The call for applications is open to anyone with links to the field of craftsmanship (professionals, students) or an interest in tangible and intangible cultural heritage, tourism, rural development, collaborative networks and related areas, who wishes to learn and share knowledge.

Participation is voluntary; the organisers will cover the necessary travel expenses—within Asturias—as well as accommodation and meals.

Each applicant may submit a single proposal to participate. It is essential that the ideas submitted are open to the participation of other people who can join as collaborators and contribute to, complement or transform the idea during the production workshop.

Once the ideas have been selected, a call for applications will be launched for those wishing to collaborate on their development. From there, working groups will be formed, comprising the person promoting the idea and the registered collaborators, with a maximum of six people per idea.

How can I submit my proposal?

By completing the form available via the link below xxxxx.

We recommend using an online form that includes the following sections.

- Name and age:
- Address:
- Email address and telephone number:
- Are you a member of any association or organisation?:
- Title of the idea:
- Motivation – Why are you applying for this call for proposals?
- Brief description of the idea (What is to be developed and where? What is the expected contribution and impact, taking into account the areas mentioned in the call?):

If you have any queries or encounter difficulties when submitting proposals, and in order to reduce any technological, linguistic or other barriers that may hinder participation in this call for proposals, interested parties may contact us at:

Email: info@laponte.org

Tel.: xxxxxxx

Criteria for the selection of ideass

- Preference will be given to ideas that can be developed in rural areas of Asturias.
- The idea must fall within the areas specified in the call for proposals.
- Clarity and specificity: the idea must be described in precise terms.
- Feasibility: it must be possible to produce an initial version or prototype by the end of the workshop.
- Originality and innovation: novel or distinctive proposals will be favoured.
- The idea must be sustainable over time and capable of being replicated in similar contexts.

The selection of ideas will be published on the scheduled date on the Ecomuseum's website and via its communication channels. Furthermore, all those who have submitted proposals for this call will be notified by email.

Timetable

- Call for ideas: xxx
- Publication of selected ideas: xxx
- Call for contributors: xxx
- Publication of contributors: xxx
- In-person prototyping workshop: xxx

The organisation's commitments

- Provide transport and/or accommodation for participants from Asturias for the entire duration of the in-person workshop.
- Provide daily meals for participants on all days of the in-person workshop.
- Make available the spaces, infrastructure, equipment and materials necessary for the work sessions.
- Provide the necessary staff for coordination, facilitation and mentoring.
- Provide resources for documenting the process.
- Provide resources for disseminating the results.
- Provide a certificate of participation to those who request it.
- Promote an open culture and share the project's processes and results publicly and accessibly.

Participant commitments

- Participation in the workshop is voluntary throughout its duration. No remuneration will be provided to organisers or contributors, and participation does not establish any employment relationship with the organising body.
- Attend all working sessions on the scheduled dates, as well as activities related to the prototype production process.
- Document the process using the tools provided by the organisation and disseminate the knowledge generated so that it is available under an open licence.

- Publicly present the prototypes developed on the final day of the workshop and make them available for public display.
- Maintain a respectful attitude towards all participants. Expressions of intolerance or discrimination on the grounds of gender, ethnicity, diversity, social status, sexual orientation, religion, origin, ideology or any other circumstance will not be tolerated.
- Recognise the participation and contributions of each member of the working group.
- Take care of the materials, tools, furniture and spaces during the lab.
- Participants must licence their creations and any derivative material (texts, photographs, videos, etc.) under a Creative Commons licence that permits derivative works and requires the use of the same licence for their redistribution.

Disclaimer

Where applicable, it shall be the responsibility of the project organiser to obtain the necessary authorisations for the use of any element of the project that requires permission under legislation on copyright and related rights.

The organisation accepts no liability for the use of data or content employed by participants, nor for any copyright or other rights belonging to third parties under current legislation. During the course of the workshop, the organisation may provide any clarifications it deems necessary to specify the established conditions. Participation in this call for entries implies acceptance of all its terms and conditions.

■ ANNEX II EXAMPLE OF A CALL FOR COLLABORATORS

Introduction

Following the selection of ideas submitted by project leaders for the **Culturalitylab: Traditional Crafts and Knowledge, Heritage Assets for Sustainable Tourism in Rural Areas**, the La Ponte Research Centre and Ecomuseum invites those interested to take part in the development of prototypes at the experimental laboratory to be held in Villanueva de Santo Adriano, Asturias, in September 2026.

What does this call for collaborators consist of?

You can use this form (add link to form) to register to take part in the workshop to prototype one of the following selected ideas:

- Idea 1
- Idea 2
- Idea 3
- Idea 4

If you have any questions or encounter any difficulties with your application for this call for entries, please contact us at:

Email: info@laponte.org

Tel.: xxxxxxxx

Timetable

Call for contributors: xxx

Confirmation of contributors: xxx

In-person prototyping workshop: xxx

Finally, add points *The organisation's commitments*, *Participant commitments* and *Disclaimer* to the call for ideas.

■ ANNEX III

LAB CUBE, PROTOTYPE, USE AND CONSTRUCTION GUIDE

What is a *Lab Cube*?

It is a tool for documentation and reflection that accompanies the entire workshop process.

It is neither a final outcome nor an assessment tool, but a living work tool:

- you write, draw, cross things out and go back,
- you work in phases,
- it allows for contradictions, changes of direction and reformulations.

Documentation is part of the experimental process itself: it is not something done at the end.

General instructions for use:

- It is not necessary to 'fill in' all the pages 100%.
- Answers are provisional and may change.
- You can return to previous pages when necessary..
- There are no right or wrong answers.

The role of the documentarian is to support the use of the cube, resolve queries and facilitate the process, never to direct the content.

The following material is attached, which serves:

1. as a guide for the facilitator and
2. as a standalone document that can be handed out to the teams if desired.

Lab Cube.

INSTRUCTIONS FOR THE *LAB CUBE*

This document explains the purpose of each side of the Lab Cube and how to use it, without turning it into a rigid method or a form.

It can be used:

- as an internal project manual,
- or as a light-touch guide for participating teams.

Face 1. Team

What is it for?

To establish the starting point: the idea as it stands now and the team behind it.

This section allows us to put a face to the people involved, analyse their profiles — particularly their strengths and weaknesses in relation to the idea — and identify what technical, methodological or support needs the team may have: what it has and what it lacks.

What is expected of the team

- A straightforward description of the idea, without justifying it.
- An initial recognition of strengths and limitations.
- Identification of gaps or necessary profiles.

How to provide guidance (if necessary)

- Encourage them to describe the idea as it stands, not to try to convince. Be honest about the team's shortcomings.

Face 2. Problem definition

What is it for?

This section acts as a strategic compass for the team.

Its aim is not merely to analyse the idea, but to identify potential directions for the work based on the team's current position.

It allows you to position yourself at a central point—the here and now of the team and the idea—and observe:

- which elements stem from the past and shape the idea,
- which scenarios open up for the future and present challenges and opportunities for the idea,
- and regarding which factors there is greater or lesser capacity to influence.

How the compass works

This section is organised around a central point:

- The centre represents the team's and the idea's current situation.
- The horizontal axis acts as a timeline:
 - Looking back (bottom of the circle): legacy factors that influence us
Weaknesses—address / Strengths—maintain
 - Forward (top of the circle): future scenarios, risks and opportunities
Threats—address / Opportunities—exploit

- The interdependencies, represented by a circle surrounding the centre, show which factors, institutions, contexts or resources the idea depends on:
 - the closer to the centre, the greater the capacity to influence that element;
 - the further away or outside the circle, the less control the team has.

The whole should be read as a guidance tool, not as a fixed list. Lines should be drawn on it, like routes showing possible paths that could be followed.

This section helps to visualise which directions make sense to move in, which ones should be reinforced and which ones require caution.

When creating it, the use of colour codes is recommended, so that the result is clear and does not become a confusing diagram. When done well, this section acts as a true compass for the process.

What is expected of the team

- Identifying real risks and opportunities.
- Recognising key dependencies and interdependencies.
- Building a shared vision to guide the team.

How to provide guidance

- Emphasise the idea of orientation rather than classification.
- Help distinguish between what can be triggered or corrected and what must be accepted as an external condition.

Face 3. Reframe

What is it for?

To reframe the idea based on what has been learned during the problem-formulation phase.

What is expected of the team

- The emergence of genuine discoveries, not just confirmations.
- Visible changes between iterations.
- Accepting that the initial idea may change significantly.

How to provide guidance

- Remind the team that they can return to Face 2 as many times as necessary.
- Ask what has changed in their understanding of the problem.

Face 4. Prototyping

What is it for?

To move from reflection to action.

The prototype must be viable, scalable and capable of being tested during the workshop. If it is not, then it is not a prototype.

What is expected of the team

- To produce something concrete: an object, an action, a story, a test, a demonstration.
- To accept the provisional and the unfinished.

How to provide guidance

- Minimise explanation and encourage experimentation.
- Remember that the prototype is not the final result.

Face 5. Testing

What is it for?

To test the prototype in the real world.

It allows you to verify its validity and assess whether the idea is feasible, scalable or sustainable.

What is expected of the team

- Define what you want to test, how (method) and with whom.
- Acknowledge failures and lessons learned.
- Treat failure as part of the process.

How to provide guidance

- View mistakes as valuable information.
- Avoid forcing something to 'work'.

Face 6. Communication

What is it for?

To communicate the process and the proposal to other audiences.

What is expected of the team

- Explain the problem the proposal addresses.
- Identify who it matters to.
- Consider impact and sustainability.

How to provide guidance

- Help the team move beyond their internal jargon or language.
- Link the proposal to the common good.
- Encourage reflection on the future: how the idea can be sustained.

Specific role of the documentation specialist

- Explain how to use the *Lab Cube* at the start of the workshop.
- Remind participants of its use throughout the process.
- Answer questions without imposing answers.
- Ensure that all stages are documented.
- Supplement the *Lab Cube* with external observations.

CONSTRUCTING THE CUBE

To make a cube, you either need to print a template onto card or use a cardboard box, writing the following headings on each side for the teams to fill in.

Lab Cube text

Face 1. Team

Idea.

Team.

Team strengths.

Team weaknesses.

Who might we need?

Face 2. Problem definition

Threats — address.

Weaknesses — address.

Opportunities — exploit.

Strengths — maintain.

Interdependencies.

Face 3. Reframe

(Return to Face 2 as many times as necessary, up to 3 iterations).

We hadn't realised that...

We discovered that...

We were surprised that...

1st iteration.

2nd iteration.

3rd iteration.

Revised idea.

Based on the above, we propose changes or new ideas.

1st iteration.

2nd iteration.

3rd iteration.

Face 4. Prototyping

No structure, no instructions.

Face 5. Test

What did we test, and how?

Works / Doesn't work.

Lessons learned.

Face 6. Communication

Gallery.

Need.

Matters to whom?

Public good generated.

Sustainability and continuity.

CULTURA

CULTURAL HERITAGE IN RURAL
REMOTE AREAS FOR CREATIVE
TOURISM AND SUSTAINABILITY

